

METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL MOBILITY OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED BELT WRESTLERS

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Abstract: this article presents quite scientific innovations on the methodology of the development of technical and tactical mobility of highly qualified wrestlers in the training process.

Keywords: highly qualified, wrestlers, training, process, technical and tactical, mobile, development, methodology.

МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ ТЕХНИКО-ТАКТИЧЕСКОЙ МОБИЛЬНОСТИ БОРЦОВ НА ПОЯСАХ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ.

Аннотация: в данной статье представлены вполне научные новации по методике развития технико-тактической мобильности борцов высокой квалификации в тренировочном процессе.

Ключевые слова: высокая квалификация, борцы, подготовка, процесс, технико-тактический, мобильный, развитие, методика.

As the relevance of the topic has been established and formed for centuries by each nation and nation on a global scale, as well as the specific types of national struggle in Uzbekistan, the types of national wrestling, which were held in the “Bukhara” and “Fergana” way, have become widely popular. In particular, wrestling is considered one of the sports that are gaining popularity, developing on all continents of the world. Currently, in most countries of the world, there are sports close to or similar to Wrestling, which is why it is important to further develop this sport on a global scale, to scientifically substantiate the system of training wrestlers.

The object of the study was the process of training, carried out in the application of the methodology for the development of technical and tactical mobility of highly qualified belt wrestlers in the training process.

Literature on the topic of the study is among the pressing problems on the basis of a new scientific and theoretical approach to preparing for the competitive activities of talented belt wrestlers, sorting into the many-year stages of training. In solving this problem, a number of local scientists conducted scientific research. In Particular, J.M. Nurshin, R.S. Salamow, F.A. Kerimov, T.C. Usmankhojaev, A.Sh. Abdullaev, Sh.X. Hankeldiev and others conducted scientific research and developed a new proposal and recommendations on the basis of a system of sorting themselves in textbooks, manuals, articles and theses. F. On problems aimed at narrow and local issues of struggle. A. Kerimov, N.M. Yusupov, SH.A. Abdullaev, R.D. Halmukhamedov, V.N. SHin, G.B. Abdurasulova, S.C. Tajibaev, J.M. Nurshin, SH.A. Mirzakulov, A.R. Taimuratov, N.A. Tastanov, Z.S. The results of the study conducted by the artikovs are of particular note.

Z from the results of the dissertation research, which is aimed at determining and assessing the indicators of general and special physical fitness of athletes in Solo sports. B. Boltaev, Z.S. Artikov, S.S. Tajibaev, M.M. Kyrgyzboev, H. Yu. Matnazarov, currently used in this area.

A number of studies conducted on the topic in the Commonwealth of Independent States and abroad N.P. Dudin, V.A. Zaporozhanov R.N. Dorokhov, V.P. Guba, Platonova V.N, N.J, Bulgakova, V.P. Guba, S.G. Fomin, S.V. Chernov Fukuda, D. Kelly, J. Albuquerque, M. Stout, J. Hoffman J. Samuel, David Grácio Pedro, Paulo Martins, and many others have done research.

Highly qualified wrestling belt wrestlers, the development of technical and tactical actions in the wrestling competition is an urgent problem. In order to solve this problem, the opinion of specialists is also important. As an expert, wrestling coaches in Namangan province were addressed and interviewed, with 18 of the coaches participating in the poll. The survey was given 20 opinions, the rate of accession to the same opinion was studied in percentage terms (№1jadval).

To find out the opinion of specialists on the impact of the development of special physical qualities during the development of technical and tactical actions of the survey:

1. The result of the merger of 85.6% with a deviation of 11.3 was shown to the idea that the development of the quality of power for the development of technical and tactical actions in the wrestling competitions will have a good effect. It is seen that high-level mergers and expert opinion are almost uniform. Hence the strength of physical qualities, he stressed that it occupies an important place in specialists – for the development of technical and tactical actions.

2. In wrestling competitions, a result of 82.4% was recorded with a deviation of 10.8 li to the idea that the development of the quality of speed for the development of technical and tactical actions will have a good effect. It has been shown that the development of speed quality has an important place in the development of technical and tactical actions.

3. In wrestling competitions, a result of 86.2% was recorded with a deviation of 14.5 li to the idea that the development of the quality of endurance for the development of technical and tactical actions will have a good effect. It has been shown that the development of the quality of endurance has an important place in the development of technical and tactical actions.

Table - 1

Highly qualified belt wrestlers ' poll results in the development of technical and tactical moves in the ring competition (n=18)

№	Questions	Average (%)	Moderate deviation (V %)
1.	for the development of technical and tactical actions in wrestling competitions, the development of the quality of strength will pay off well	85,6	11,3
2.	for the development of technical and tactical actions in wrestling competitions, the development of the quality of speed will have a good effect	82,4	10,8
3.	The development of the quality of endurance for the development of technical and tactical actions in wrestling competitions will pay off well	86,2	14,5
4.	The development of the quality of flexibility for the development of technical and tactical actions in wrestling competitions will pay off well	72,5	14,5
5.	The development of the quality of agility for the development of technical and tactical actions in wrestling competitions will have a good effect	88,5	12,2

6.	It is necessary to take into account the rules of the competition in the development of technical and tactical actions		100	0
7.	It is necessary to assess the conditions for conducting the competition in the development of technical and tactical actions		91,4	3,6
8.	In the development of technical and tactical actions, it is necessary to assess the weather conditions at the time of conducting the competition		76,8	11,7
9.	To develop technical and tactical actions, it will work well to prepare before the competition, relying on the information obtained on the basis of the “intelligence” style, having mastered the methods of the horns of the participating opponents		100	0
10.	It is necessary not to waste time on actions that are not necessary during the development of technical and tactical actions		100	0
11.	In the competition, it is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the first stage of multi-year readiness(base training) with the struggle		12,4	24,5
12.	It is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the second stage of multi-year readiness(deepening into the specialty) with the struggle		78,3	16,7
13.	It is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the third stage of multi-year readiness(improvement in sports) with the struggle		82,5	15,2
14.	It is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the fourth stage of multi-year readiness(higher sports skills) with the struggle		100	0
15.	In the competition, it is advisable to improve the technical and tactical actions at the first stage of multi-year readiness(base training) with the struggle		0	0
16.	It is advisable to improve technical and tactical actions at the second stage of many years of readiness (deepening into the specialty) with the struggle		52,6	17,4
17.	It is advisable to improve technical and tactical actions at the third stage of multi-year readiness(improvement in sports) with the fight struggle		100	0
18.	It is advisable to improve technical and tactical actions at the fourth stage of multi-year readiness(higher sports skills) with the fight struggle		100	0
19.	At the first stage of many years of preparation stepped combination movements work well	two	95,2	22,5
		three	66,8	25,2
		four	32,1	31,7
		more than four	0	0
20.		two	100	0
		three	92,4	18,5

	In the second stage of multi-year preparation stepped combination movements work well	four	71,6	21,4
		more than four	53,5	24,7
21.	In the third stage of multi-year preparation stepped combination movements work well	two	100	0
		three	100	0
		four	88,6	14,8
		more than four	73,5	15,4
22.	In the fourth stage of multi-year preparation stepped combination movements work well	two	100	0
		three	100	0
		four	100	0
		more than four	93,7	18,5

4. The result of 72.5% with a deviation of 14.5 li was noted to the opinion that the development of the quality of flexibility for the development of technical and tactical actions in wrestling competitions will have a good effect. It has been shown that the development of the quality of flexibility is not very high in the development of technical and tactical actions.

5. In wrestling competitions, an 88.5% result was recorded with a deviation of 12.2 li to the idea that the development of the quality of agility for the development of technical and tactical actions will have a good effect. It has been shown that the development of the quality of agility has a very important place in the development of technical and tactical actions.

The following points were studied to what extent wrestling belt wrestlers occupy an important place in their competition activities, preparatory stages, when processing tactical styles:

6. In the development of technical and tactical actions, a result of 100% was recorded without deviation from the idea that it is necessary to take into account the rules of the competition. It is noted that taking into account the rules of the competition has a very important place in the development of technical and tactical actions.

7. A result of 91.4% was recorded with a deviation of 3.6 to the idea that it is necessary to assess the conditions for conducting the competition in the development of its technical and tactical actions. It has been argued that competitive conditions have an important place in the development of technical and tactical actions.

8. A result of 76.8% was recorded with an 11.7 deviation from the idea that it is necessary to assess the weather conditions at the time of conducting the competition in the development of its technical and tactical actions. Taking into account the weather conditions at the time of conducting the competition does not affect the development of technical and tactical actions to such an extent, but it seems that it is necessary not to forget about this factor.

9. A result of 100% was recorded without deviation from the idea that it will work well to prepare, relying on data obtained on the basis of the "intelligence" style before the competition to develop technical and tactical actions, while using the Horn methods of the participating opponents. It has been argued that the pre-race "reconnaissance" style has the most important place in the development of technical-tactical actions.

10. A result of 100% was recorded without deviation from the idea that it is necessary not to waste time on actions that are not necessary during the development of technical and tactical

actions. Of course, experts expressed an opinion in the case when it was intended not to waste time on performing actions that were not needed in excess.

11. The competition recorded a result of 12.4% with a deviation of 24.5 to the idea that it is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the first stage of multi-year readiness (base training) with the struggle. Apparently, most experts did not agree with this opinion. One of the main reasons is that at the first stage, the initial preparatory groups are engaged, in the training tasks in which the technical and tactical actions will not be fully formed.

12. A result of 78.3% with a deviation of 16.7 was noted to the opinion that it is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the second stage of multi-year readiness (deepening to the specialty) with the struggle. There is an addition of specialists to this opinion. One of the reasons for this is that in the second stage, training groups are engaged, in the training tasks in which, if the technical and tactical actions are incomplete, Ham will be formed.

13. A result of 82.5% with a deviation of 15.2 was noted to the opinion that it is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the third stage of multi-year readiness with struggle (improvement in sports). The addition of specialists to this opinion is at a high level. The reason is that at the third stage, improvement groups are engaged in sports, in the training tasks in which the technical and tactical actions will be fully formed.

14. A result of 100% was recorded without deviation from the idea that it is advisable to develop technical and tactical actions at the fourth stage of multi-year readiness with the struggle (higher sports skills). The inclusion of specialists in this opinion is at the highest level. The reason is that at the fourth stage, higher sports skills groups are engaged, in the training tasks in which the technical and tactical actions are fully formed, it is decided to improve them more and more and achieve higher results.

15. Hech kim did not agree with the idea that it is advisable to improve technical and tactical actions in the competition at the first stage of multi-year readiness with the fight (base training). The reason is that without the development of technical and tactical actions, it is impossible to climb to the stage of improvement.

16. The opinion that it is advisable to improve technical and tactical actions at the second stage of multi-year readiness with the struggle (deepening into the specialty), was added by 52.6% of respondents with a deviation of 17.4. The reason for the low level is that at the second stage, belt wrestlers, only some talented ones can move to the stage of improvement after development.

17. The opinion that it is advisable to improve technical and tactical actions at the third stage of multi-year readiness with the fight struggle (improvement in sports), the respondents noted a result of 100% without deviation. In sports, opinions are taken into account based on the task in improvement groups.

18. Ham respondents who noted a result of 100% without deviations to the opinion that it is advisable to improve technical and tactical actions at the fourth stage of multi-year readiness with struggle (higher sports skills). The reason is the phrase "there is no limit to improvement" and the tasks set before the higher sports skill groups are aimed at achieving higher sports results.

19.1. In the first stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 95.2% was recorded with a deviation of 4.8 to the idea that two-step combination actions will work well.

19.2. In the first stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 66.8% was recorded with a deviation of 25.2 to the idea that three-step combination actions will work well.

19.3. In the first stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 32.1% was recorded with a deviation of 31.7 to the idea that four-step combination actions will work well.

19.4. did not agree with the idea that in the first stage of many years of preparation, combination actions with more than four steps will work well.

20.1. In the second stage of multi-year preparation, all respondents were added without deviation to the idea that two-step combination actions will work well.

20.2. In the second phase of multi-year training, 92.4% of specialists contributed to the opinion that three-step combination actions work well, the deviation indicator in it was 18.5%.

20.3. In the second stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 71.6% was recorded with a deviation of 21.4 to the idea that four-step combination actions will work well.

20.4. In the second stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 53.5% was recorded with a deviation of 24.7 to the idea that combination actions with more than four steps will work well.

21.1. and 21.2. according to the opinion, the opinion that two- and three-step combination actions in the third stage of multi-year training will work well, the respondents recorded a result of 100% without deviations.

21.3. In the third stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 88.6% was recorded with a deviation of 14.8 to the idea that four-step combination actions will work well.

21.4. In the third stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 73.5% was recorded with a deviation of 15.4 to the idea that four-step combination actions will work well.

22.1., 22.2., 22.3. according to their opinion, the opinion that the combined two-, three- and four-step effort in the fourth stage of multi-year training will work well, the respondents recorded a result of 100% without deviations.

22.4. In the fourth stage of multi-year preparation, a result of 93.7% was recorded with a deviation of 18.5 to the idea that combination actions with more than four steps will work well.

Conclusion based on the results of the above survey, it can be said that all physical qualities occupy an important place in the development of technical and tactical actions in the competition of wrestling belt wrestlers. Especially experts have emphasized the quality of agility more. The reason is the response movement by the opponent to each action, which requires the opponent's response movement to work on this quality by arranging a cell with other actions using the quality of agility in time.

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